

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

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Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- Other**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Publishable Executive Summary

This document is the description of the design process for deliverable **D8.4 – Project Video** of the BioReCer project, due in M18. The deliverable is related to tasks **T8.2. Dissemination Activities** and **T8.3. Communications Activities** (Month 1–36) both led by NOVA. The project video follows the goal to communicate the overall objective of the BioReCer project in an easy to understand and visually appealing way. The video addresses multiple stakeholder groups and target audiences, e.g. the bio-based industries, certification bodies and policy makers, but mainly the general public.

The document provides an overview of the defined goals and objectives of the deliverable, its structure as well as the process of video creation.

It further contains a link to the final video version, which is available on the project website, will be uploaded into the YouTube channels of various entities and circulated via multiple digital channels, such as social media (LinkedIn and Twitter).

1 Agency Selection

To ensure a responsible spending of tax payer money, NOVA requested and compared the service packages and price offers of three video agencies. Considering the size of the consortium plus high number of participating individuals, and the budget restrictions, the contract was awarded to the German video agency Videohelden, as their offer included unlimited feedback rounds, which was paramount in this case. The offer includes a fully animated video with voiceover, a variety of possible styles and voices to choose from, additional graphical material and stills that can be used for subsequent visual communication, and an infinite number of feedback rounds.

2 Deliverable Objectives

The BioReCer video follows the overall objective to present complex scientific content and structure of the project in a short, visualised, easy to understand and clear manner. It addresses multiples stakeholder groups and especially the general public, while at the same time being of value to bio-economy industry stakeholders and the scientific community. The ideal length was determined to be 60 seconds.

2.1 Target Audience

In agreement with the team of the project coordinator Cetaqua, the decision was made to create a video that primarily addresses the general public. The current version therefore covers general sustainability goals and opportunities of bio-waste utilisation and certification in an easy-to-understand way, while still providing details and information that can be of interest to industry stakeholders and the scientific community.

2.2 Key Elements, Key-Messages and Content

Prior to the start of the video creation, the consortium together with NOVA identified the key elements and messages needed to be addressed.

Key topics included:

- Mitigation of climate change,
- Substitution of fossil resources with bio-bases alternatives,
- Potential of bio-waste,
- Insufficient certification of bio-based/waste feedstock
- Assessment of current certification schemes,
- Development of novel certification guidelines
- The Bioresources Innovation Ecosystem Living-Lab which embraces the BRSP and the BioReCer ICT Tool
- Fostering the circular EU bioeconomy.

Mandatory elements further included:

- BioReCer logo,
- Partner logos,
- EU logo with funding statement and disclaimer.

2.3 Diversity and Inclusion

The agreement also emphasised the importance of gender equality, diversity, inclusive language and an engaging presentation. It is also kept straightforward so that is also accessible to non-experts. To make the content available to people with hearing disabilities, the video further includes English subtitles.

Figure 1: Diversity Implementation in the BioReCer Video

3 Script, Design Board and Animation

The video's content and visuals should be easy to understand without any additional information on the BioReCer project. Based on the input provided by the consortium and the project coordinator, a script including an illustration concept (in English and German) with 14 scenes was created and approved after various amendments.

In the next step, based on the objectives and the key topics and mandatory elements, a style-frame was developed for the entire video, which served as basis for the subsequent animation.

Figure 2: Impressions BioReCer Video Design Board

4 Voiceover

Preceding the animation of the video, a selection of male and female voice samples was provided by the video agency. From this pool, NOVA selected a female speaker called “Holly” originating from UK, considering British English as the official communication language in EU projects. The narrator offers a distinct and recognisable voice communicating competence and confidence.

5 Video Availability

The final video version was embedded on the front page of the project website <https://biorecer.eu>.

It was further uploaded to the NOVA YouTube channel <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hi5CVZpkV2k> and made available via the open access repository Zendo <https://zenodo.org/records/10679065>.

In addition, the video was made available to all partners for upload on their specific websites via the project's share folder.

The video will be promoted with a mid-term press release scheduled for June 2024, supportive social media activity and will be incorporated in future event presentations of the BioReCer project.

Figure 3: Impressions Final Project Video

6 Conclusion

Creating a project video allows the consortium to communicate the complex structure and objectives of the BioReCer project to a broad audience in less than 60 seconds by using a visualised and easy to-understand-form.

It will support the partners in disseminating and communicating project related information in an appealing way.

The video was delivered in due time.

7 List of Abbreviations

BioReCer	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes
BIT	BIORECER IoT Tool
BRIE-LL	BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living-Lab
BRSP	BioResources Stakeholders Platform
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
NOVA	nova-Institute for political and environmental innovation GmbH
T	Task

